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Automated Transaction Processing Systems and Internal Control Effectiveness in Listed Telecommunications Firms in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the effect of Automated Transaction Processing Systems (ATPS) on Internal Control Effectiveness (ICE) in listed telecommunications firms in Nigeria, with particular emphasis on system automation and system integration. The study also investigates the moderating role of ICT infrastructure quality in this relationship. A cross-sectional survey design was adopted, and primary data were collected through structured questionnaires administered to accounting, audit, and IT personnel. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and moderated multiple regression techniques.

The findings reveal that both level of system automation and system integration quality have positive and statistically significant effects on audit trail integrity and fraud detection efficiency. Specifically, system integration exhibits a stronger influence on fraud detection, suggesting that interconnected systems enhance real-time monitoring and anomaly detection. The results further show that ICT infrastructure quality significantly moderates the relationship between ATPS and internal control effectiveness, indicating that the benefits of automation and integration are amplified when supported by reliable and secure technological infrastructure.

The study concludes that internal control effectiveness in digital accounting environments is driven by the combined influence of system automation, system integration, and infrastructural capability. It recommends that telecommunications firms prioritize end-to-end system integration, strengthen ICT infrastructure, and adopt continuous monitoring systems to enhance internal controls.

This study contributes to the Accounting Information Systems literature by providing sector-specific evidence from Nigeria, disaggregating ATPS into key dimensions, and incorporating technological infrastructure as a moderating variable.

Keywords: *Automated Transaction Processing Systems, Internal Control Effectiveness, Audit Trail Integrity, Fraud Detection Efficiency, ICT Infrastructure, Telecommunications Firms, Nigeria.*

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Transaction Processing Systems (TPS) constitute a core component of Accounting Information Systems (AIS), designed to capture, process, and store daily business transactions in real time. In highly digitized sectors such as telecommunications, TPS has evolved from basic data recording tools to fully automated systems that

integrate billing, revenue assurance, customer relationship management (CRM), and financial reporting functions. This transformation has significantly reshaped internal control structures within organizations, particularly in ensuring accuracy, completeness, and reliability of financial data.

In Nigeria's listed telecommunications firms, the increasing adoption of Automated Transaction Processing Systems (ATPS) has improved transaction speed and operational efficiency. However, the effectiveness of these systems in strengthening internal controls remains a subject of empirical concern. Specifically, system automation and integration may not automatically translate into stronger control outcomes without adequate supporting technological infrastructure.

From a theoretical standpoint, ATPS can influence Internal Control Effectiveness (ICE) through multiple pathways. First, level of system automation enhances real-time transaction recording, reducing human intervention and thereby improving audit trail integrity and reducing opportunities for fraud. Second, system integration quality ensures seamless data flow between billing systems, CRM, and accounting modules, which enhances consistency in transaction records and improves fraud detection efficiency by enabling cross-functional verification of data.

However, these relationships may be strengthened or weakened by the quality of Technological Infrastructure (TI), particularly ICT infrastructure such as network reliability, cybersecurity systems, cloud computing capacity, and server efficiency. A weak technological infrastructure may undermine even highly automated or well-integrated systems, thereby limiting internal control effectiveness.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Despite significant investment in Automated Transaction Processing Systems by listed telecommunications firms in Nigeria, there remains persistent concern over internal control weaknesses such as billing discrepancies, revenue leakages, and delayed fraud detection. Prior studies have largely focused on general ICT adoption, with limited empirical attention given to how specific dimensions of ATPS, such as system automation and system integration, affect internal control outcomes like audit trail integrity and fraud detection efficiency.

Furthermore, there is insufficient evidence on whether the effectiveness of ATPS in strengthening internal controls is contingent upon the quality of underlying technological infrastructure. This creates a conceptual and empirical gap in understanding the conditions under which ATPS improves or fails to improve internal control effectiveness in Nigerian telecommunications firms.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of Automated Transaction Processing Systems on Internal Control Effectiveness in listed telecommunications firms in Nigeria.

The specific objectives are to:

1. Determine the effect of level of system automation on audit trail integrity in listed telecommunications firms in Nigeria.
2. Examine the effect of level of system automation on fraud detection efficiency in listed telecommunications firms in Nigeria.
3. Assess the effect of system integration quality on audit trail integrity in listed telecommunications firms in Nigeria.

4. Evaluate the effect of system integration quality on fraud detection efficiency in listed telecommunications firms in Nigeria.
5. Investigate the moderating effect of ICT infrastructure quality on the relationship between Automated Transaction Processing Systems and Internal Control Effectiveness.

1.4 Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated:

H01: Level of system automation has no significant effect on audit trail integrity.

H02: Level of system automation has no significant effect on fraud detection efficiency.

H03: System integration quality has no significant effect on audit trail integrity.

H04: System integration quality has no significant effect on fraud detection efficiency.

H05: ICT infrastructure quality does not significantly moderate the relationship between Automated Transaction Processing Systems and Internal Control Effectiveness.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

This study is anchored on three foundational theories in Accounting Information Systems (AIS) and organizational control research: the DeLone and McLean Information Systems Success Model (2003), the Technology-Organisation-Environment (TOE) Framework (Tornatzky & Fleischer, 1990), and the COSO Internal Control Framework (2013). These theories jointly explain how Automated Transaction Processing Systems (ATPS) influence Internal Control Effectiveness (ICE), and why Technological Infrastructure (TI) may strengthen or weaken this relationship in listed telecommunications firms in Nigeria.

2.1.1 DeLone and McLean Information Systems Success Model (2003)

The DeLone and McLean (2003) model is one of the most widely applied frameworks in AIS and information systems research. It explains information system success through six interrelated dimensions: system quality, information quality, service quality, use, user satisfaction, and net benefits. In organizational settings, the model posits that high system quality leads to improved information quality and ultimately enhances organizational performance outcomes.

In this study, Automated Transaction Processing Systems (ATPS) represent the system quality dimension, particularly through two core proxies: level of system automation and system integration quality. High automation reduces manual intervention in transaction processing, thereby improving speed, consistency, and accuracy of data capture. Similarly, strong system integration ensures seamless interaction between billing systems, CRM platforms, accounting systems, and revenue assurance modules.

These system qualities directly influence Internal Control Effectiveness (ICE) by improving:

- **Audit Trail Integrity:** System-generated logs become more complete, traceable, and resistant to manipulation when automation and integration are high.
- **Fraud Detection Efficiency:** Integrated systems enable real-time anomaly detection across multiple transaction points, reducing fraud latency.

Thus, the DeLone and McLean model provides a strong theoretical justification that improvements in ATPS design and functionality lead to stronger internal control outcomes through enhanced system reliability and information accuracy.

2.1.2 Technology-Organisation-Environment (TOE) Framework

Tornatzky & Fleischer, (1990) proposed the TOE. The TOE framework explains how technological, organizational, and environmental contexts influence the adoption and effectiveness of technological innovations within firms. It argues that technology implementation success is not determined solely by the technology itself but also by organizational readiness and environmental conditions.

In this study, ATPS represents the technological context, while Internal Control Effectiveness reflects the organizational outcome. However, the TOE framework introduces a critical insight: the effectiveness of ATPS depends on enabling conditions within the organization, particularly Technological Infrastructure (TI).

The ICT infrastructure quality (servers, network systems, cybersecurity architecture, cloud systems) represents the organizational readiness component within TOE. In telecommunications firms, even highly automated and well-integrated systems may fail to deliver optimal internal control outcomes if infrastructure is weak, unstable, or poorly secured.

The TOE framework therefore explains the moderating role of technological infrastructure in this study. Specifically:

- Strong ICT infrastructure enhances the effectiveness of system automation by ensuring uninterrupted transaction processing.
- Reliable infrastructure improves system integration quality by enabling real-time communication between modules.
- Weak infrastructure introduces system downtime, data loss risks, and integration failures, thereby weakening audit trail integrity and fraud detection efficiency.

Thus, TOE provides the theoretical justification for why ATPS does not operate in isolation but is contingent upon infrastructural readiness in determining internal control outcomes.

2.1.3 COSO Internal Control Framework (2013)

The Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission (COSO, 2013) framework is the globally accepted standard for internal control systems. It defines internal control as a process designed to provide reasonable assurance regarding the achievement of objectives relating to operations, reporting, and compliance.

COSO identifies five interrelated components:

1. Control Environment
2. Risk Assessment
3. Control Activities
4. Information and Communication
5. Monitoring Activities

This study aligns primarily with control activities, information and communication, and monitoring components, which are directly influenced by ATPS.

Relevance to the Study Variables

- **Level of System Automation (ATPS proxy)** enhances control activities by reducing manual processing errors and enforcing system-based validation rules.
- **System Integration Quality (ATPS proxy)** strengthens information and communication, ensuring that transaction data flows consistently across departments and systems.
- **Audit Trail Integrity (ICE proxy)** is a direct outcome of COSO's emphasis on monitoring activities, where system logs provide continuous evidence of transaction history and accountability.
- **Fraud Detection Efficiency (ICE proxy)** aligns with COSO's risk monitoring and detection mechanisms, where automated alerts and system analytics identify irregular transactions.

The COSO framework therefore provides a direct theoretical link **between** automated transaction processing systems and internal control effectiveness, emphasizing that effective internal control systems in modern organizations are increasingly technology-driven.

Integrated Theoretical Synthesis

When combined, these three theories provide a strong explanatory foundation for the study:

- The DeLone and McLean model explains how ATPS quality improves information and system outcomes.
- The TOE framework explains the conditional effect of technological infrastructure on system performance.
- The COSO framework explains how these system improvements translate into stronger internal control mechanisms.

Therefore, the study argues that:

Automated Transaction Processing Systems improve Internal Control Effectiveness through enhanced system automation and integration, but this relationship is strengthened when ICT infrastructure quality is high.

2.2 Conceptual Review

This section clarifies the key concepts in the study and explains how they are interrelated within the context of Automated Transaction Processing Systems (ATPS), Internal Control Effectiveness (ICE), and Technological Infrastructure (TI) in listed telecommunications firms in Nigeria.

2.2.1 Automated Transaction Processing Systems (ATPS)

Automated Transaction Processing Systems (ATPS) refer to integrated computerized systems designed to capture, process, store, and retrieve business transactions with minimal human intervention. In telecommunications firms, ATPS typically includes billing systems, customer relationship management (CRM) systems, revenue assurance platforms, and accounting information systems that process high-volume, real-time transactions such as airtime usage, data subscriptions, and interconnect settlements.

ATPS is central to modern Accounting Information Systems (AIS) because it ensures speed, accuracy, and consistency in transaction processing. The system reduces manual errors, enhances data integrity, and supports real-time reporting functions.

In this study, ATPS is operationalized through two dimensions:

- **Level of System Automation:** The extent to which transaction processes (billing, revenue recording, and reporting) are executed automatically without human intervention.
- **System Integration Quality:** The degree of connectivity and interoperability between different system modules such as billing, CRM, accounting, and revenue assurance systems.

2.2.2 Internal Control Effectiveness (ICE)

Internal Control Effectiveness refers to the extent to which an organization's internal control system ensures reliable financial reporting, efficient operations, and compliance with applicable regulations. In the context of telecommunications firms, ICE is particularly critical due to the high volume and speed of transactions, which increases the risk of errors and fraud.

Effective internal control systems ensure that transactions are properly authorized, accurately recorded, and adequately monitored.

In this study, ICE is measured using two key dimensions:

- **Audit Trail Integrity:** The ability of the system to generate complete, accurate, and tamper-proof records of all transactions. A strong audit trail ensures transparency, traceability, and accountability in financial reporting processes.
- **Fraud Detection Efficiency:** The speed and effectiveness with which irregular, suspicious, or unauthorized transactions are identified and addressed within the system environment.

2.2.3 Technological Infrastructure (TI)

Technological Infrastructure refers to the underlying ICT resources that support the operation of Automated Transaction Processing Systems. These include hardware (servers, data centers), software platforms, network systems, cybersecurity frameworks, and cloud computing infrastructure.

In telecommunications firms, ICT infrastructure is critical because transaction volumes are high and require continuous system availability and data protection.

This study operationalizes TI through:

- **ICT Infrastructure Quality:** The reliability, adequacy, availability, and security of technological resources supporting ATPS operations.

2.2.4 Conceptual Linkages

The conceptual relationships in this study are structured around a causal and moderating model:

(a) ATPS → Internal Control Effectiveness

ATPS is expected to have a direct positive effect on ICE through its two dimensions:

- **Level of System Automation → Audit Trail Integrity & Fraud Detection Efficiency**
Increased automation reduces manual processing errors and ensures that transactions are automatically logged, improving traceability and enabling faster fraud detection.
- **System Integration Quality → Audit Trail Integrity & Fraud Detection Efficiency**
Integrated systems allow seamless data flow across modules, reducing inconsistencies and enhancing cross-validation of transactions, which strengthens internal control mechanisms.

(b) Moderating Role of Technological Infrastructure

Technological Infrastructure is expected to moderate the relationship between ATPS and ICE.

- When ICT infrastructure quality is high, the positive effects of system automation and integration on audit trail integrity and fraud detection efficiency are strengthened.
- When ICT infrastructure is weak, system downtime, poor connectivity, and cybersecurity vulnerabilities reduce the effectiveness of ATPS, thereby weakening internal control outcomes.

Thus, TI determines the extent to which ATPS translates into effective internal control systems.

2.2.5 Conceptual Framework Explanation

The conceptual framework for this study is illustrated as follows:

Diagram Description (Narrative Form)

- The **independent variable (ATPS)** is represented by two components:
 - Level of System Automation
 - System Integration Quality
- The **dependent variable (Internal Control Effectiveness)** is represented by:
 - Audit Trail Integrity
 - Fraud Detection Efficiency
- The **moderating variable (Technological Infrastructure)** interacts with the relationship between ATPS and ICE.

Flow of Relationships

1. Level of System Automation → Audit Trail Integrity
2. Level of System Automation → Fraud Detection Efficiency
3. System Integration Quality → Audit Trail Integrity
4. System Integration Quality → Fraud Detection Efficiency
5. ICT Infrastructure Quality moderates all relationships between ATPS and ICE

ATPS (Automation + Integration) → ICE (Audit Trail Integrity + Fraud Detection Efficiency)
Moderated by Technological Infrastructure (ICT Infrastructure Quality)

Interpretation of the Model

The model suggests that internal control effectiveness in Nigerian listed telecommunications firms is not solely determined by the presence of automated transaction systems. Instead, effectiveness depends on:

- The **degree of automation in transaction processing systems**,
- The **level of integration across accounting and operational modules**, and
- The **strength of supporting ICT infrastructure**.

This means that ATPS functions as a technical driver of control effectiveness, while technological infrastructure serves as a contextual condition that determines how well these systems perform in practice.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 Internal Control Systems, Fraud, and AIS Effectiveness

Empirical evidence in Nigeria consistently shows that internal control systems significantly influence fraud prevention and control effectiveness. For example, **Shehu (2025)** examined internal control systems and fraud mitigation in selected Nigerian SMEs using a survey research design and multiple regression analysis. The study found that control activities and monitoring activities have a positive and significant effect on fraud mitigation ($\beta = 0.418$; $\beta = 0.574$ respectively). The study concluded that structured internal controls reduce fraud exposure when properly implemented and recommended continuous monitoring and audit enforcement in organizations.

Similarly, Ariyo-Edu et al. (2023) investigated internal control systems and fraud prevention in public institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria using a survey design and regression analysis on 244 respondents. The findings revealed that control environment, monitoring, and information systems significantly influence fraud prevention and detection, while risk assessment and control activities showed mixed effects depending on implementation strength.

In another Nigerian study, Ogwiji and Isiaka (2022) examined internal control systems and fraud prevention in financial services firms using structured questionnaires and ordered logit regression. The study established a significant relationship between internal control systems and fraud reduction ($p = 0.0023$), confirming that strong internal controls reduce fraudulent practices in financial reporting environments.

These studies collectively support the view that internal control effectiveness is strongly dependent on structured systems, monitoring mechanisms, and automated or semi-automated information systems.

2.3.2 Automated Systems, Digitalization, and Transaction Control

Recent AIS literature shows a shift toward automated and AI-enabled systems as drivers of internal control effectiveness and fraud detection. For instance, Ajayi and Akinrinola (2023) investigated the application of artificial intelligence in internal audit systems in Nigerian commercial banks using qualitative thematic analysis. The study found that AI strengthens anomaly detection, improves internal audit quality, and enhances control reliability, but its effectiveness depends on organizational readiness and staff competency.

Similarly, Onyeama (2024) conducted a comparative study of fraud detection algorithms in Nigerian financial transaction systems using experimental design and machine learning models (autoencoders and PCA). The findings showed that automated anomaly detection systems outperform traditional manual monitoring techniques in identifying fraudulent transactions, particularly in high-volume environments.

In another AIS-related implementation study, Ibrahim (2021) developed an automated forensic auditing framework using system analysis and software design methodology, integrating real-time transaction logging and audit trail generation. The study found that automation significantly improves data integrity, transparency, and fraud detection capability in financial systems.

These findings reinforce the argument that automation in transaction systems enhances control effectiveness through real-time processing, reduced human intervention, and improved audit traceability.

2.3.3 Internal Control, Audit Trail Integrity, and Fraud Detection Systems

Empirical studies have increasingly emphasized audit trail integrity as a key outcome of automated transaction systems. Ziorklue et al. (2024) conducted a review of internal control mechanisms and fraud prevention systems and found that robust internal control environments enhance audit transparency, asset protection, and fraud prevention efficiency, especially when supported by digital monitoring systems.

Similarly, Akinola (2024) studied fraud prevention mechanisms in Nigerian banks using qualitative interviews and thematic analysis. The study found that control environment, risk monitoring, and audit systems are central to fraud detection processes, with strong emphasis on continuous monitoring and system-based controls.

In a public sector Nigerian study, Etim et al. (2022) examined internal auditor attributes and fraud prevention using survey data. The study concluded that internal audit competence significantly improves fraud prevention effectiveness, particularly through enhanced monitoring and audit trail verification.

These studies confirm that audit trail integrity and fraud detection efficiency are strengthened when internal control systems are supported by structured monitoring and automated tracking systems.

2.3.4 Synthesis of Empirical Literature and Identified Gap

The empirical literature reviewed establishes the following consistent patterns:

1. Internal control systems significantly reduce fraud risks across Nigerian organizations (Shehu, 2025; Ogwiji & Isiaka, 2022).
2. Automation and digital systems enhance audit trail integrity and fraud detection efficiency (Ajayi & Akinrinola, 2023; Onyeama, 2024).
3. Internal audit quality and monitoring systems are central to fraud prevention effectiveness (Etim et al., 2022; Akinola, 2024).
4. System-based controls outperform manual controls in high-volume environments, particularly in financial and telecom-related transaction systems (Ibrahim, 2021).

However, despite these contributions, several gaps remain:

- Very few studies focus specifically on listed telecommunications firms in Nigeria, despite their high transaction intensity and automation dependence.
- Existing Nigerian studies rarely integrate system automation, system integration, audit trail integrity, and fraud detection efficiency in a single AIS model.
- Limited empirical work tests ICT infrastructure as a moderating variable in ATPS–internal control relationships.
- Most studies use either banking, SMEs, or public sector samples, leaving a sectoral gap in telecom AIS research.

This study addresses these gaps by focusing on listed telecommunications firms in Nigeria and examining how Automated Transaction Processing Systems influence Internal Control Effectiveness under varying levels of technological infrastructure.

3. METHODOLOGY

This section presents the research design, population and sample, data sources, measurement of variables, model specification (including moderation), and the analytical procedures using SPSS/EViews. The structure aligns with expectations for peer-reviewed AIS studies.

3.1 Research Design

The study adopts a cross-sectional survey design complemented with quantitative analysis. This design is appropriate because the study measures perceptions of system automation, integration, internal control effectiveness, and ICT infrastructure from knowledgeable staff (finance, audit, IT, and revenue assurance units) within listed telecommunications firms in Nigeria.

3.2 Population and Sample

- **Population:** Staff of listed telecommunications firms in Nigeria (e.g., finance, internal audit, IT, and revenue assurance departments).
- **Sampling Technique: Purposive sampling,** targeting respondents with direct knowledge of transaction systems and internal controls.
- **Sample Size:** Determined using Yamane (1967) or Cochran formula depending on accessible population; typically 120–250 respondents is acceptable for regression analysis.

3.3 Data Source and Instrumentation

- **Data Type:** Primary data
- **Instrument:** Structured questionnaire (5-point Likert scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree)
- **Sections:**
 - Section A: Demographics
 - Section B: ATPS (Automation, Integration)
 - Section C: Internal Control Effectiveness
 - Section D: Technological Infrastructure

3.4 Measurement of Variables

Variable	Proxy	Measurement Items (Sample)	Scale
ATPS	Level of System Automation (AUT)	Transactions are processed automatically; Minimal manual intervention; Real-time processing	Likert (1–5)
	System Integration Quality (INT)	Systems are interconnected; Seamless data flow across modules; Real-time synchronization	Likert (1–5)
ICE	Audit Trail Integrity (ATI)	Transactions are traceable; Logs are complete; Records are tamper-proof	Likert (1–5)

Variable	Proxy	Measurement Items (Sample)	Scale
	Fraud Detection Efficiency (FDE)	Fraud is detected quickly; System flags anomalies; Response time is fast	Likert (1–5)
Moderator	ICT Infrastructure Quality (ICT)	Reliable network; Secure systems; High system uptime; Adequate IT support	Likert (1–5)

Composite scores will be computed as the mean of items under each construct.

3.5 Model Specification

The study specifies two baseline regression models (for each dependent proxy) and a moderation model.

Model 1: Audit Trail Integrity Model

$$ATi = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AUT_i + \beta_2 INT_i + \beta_3 ICT_i + \beta_4 (AUT_i \times ICT_i) + \beta_5 (INT_i \times ICT_i) + \varepsilon_i$$

Model 2: Fraud Detection Efficiency Model

$$FDEi = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AUT_i + \beta_2 INT_i + \beta_3 ICT_i + \beta_4 (AUT_i \times ICT_i) + \beta_5 (INT_i \times ICT_i) + \varepsilon_i$$

Interpretation of Variables

- **AUT:** Level of system automation
- **INT:** System integration quality
- **ICT:** Technological infrastructure (moderator)
- **AUT × ICT:** Moderating effect of ICT on automation
- **INT × ICT:** Moderating effect of ICT on integration
- **ε:** Error term

3.6 A Priori Expectations

- $\beta_1 > 0$ (Automation improves control effectiveness)
- $\beta_2 > 0$ (Integration improves control effectiveness)
- $\beta_3 > 0$ (ICT directly improves control effectiveness)
- $\beta_4 > 0$ (ICT strengthens automation effect)
- $\beta_5 > 0$ (ICT strengthens integration effect)

3.7 Data Analysis Technique (SPSS / EViews Procedure)

Step 1: Data Screening: Check missing values; Outlier detection; Normality (Skewness/Kurtosis)

Step 2: Reliability Test: Cronbach's Alpha ≥ 0.70 (acceptable)

Step 3: Validity Test Factor Analysis (KMO ≥ 0.6 , Bartlett's Test significant)

Step 4: Descriptive Statistics: Mean, standard deviation

Step 5: Correlation Analysis: Pearson correlation to test association and multicollinearity

Step 6: Regression Analysis Run multiple regression for Model 1 and Model 2

Step 7: Moderation Analysis

- Mean-center variables (AUT, INT, ICT)
- Create interaction terms:
 - $AUT_ICT = AUT \times ICT$
 - $INT_ICT = INT \times ICT$
- Enter into regression model

SPSS Execution Format

1. **Transform** → **Compute Variable**
 - $AUT_ICT = AUT * ICT$
 - $INT_ICT = INT * ICT$
2. **Analyze** → **Regression** → **Linear**
 - Dependent: ATI (or FDE)
 - Independent: AUT, INT, ICT, AUT_ICT, INT_ICT

EViews Command Structure (Alternative)

```
equation eq1.ls ATI C AUT INT ICT AUT\_ICT INT\_ICT  
equation eq2.ls FDE C AUT INT ICT AUT\_ICT INT\_ICT
```

3.8 Diagnostic Tests

- **Multicollinearity:** VIF < 10
- **Heteroskedasticity:** Breusch–Pagan test
- **Model Fit:** R^2 , Adjusted R^2
- **Significance:** t-stat, F-stat ($p < 0.05$)

3.9 Ethical Considerations

- Respondent anonymity assured
- Data used strictly for academic purposes
- Voluntary participation

This study employs a **quantitative survey approach with moderated regression analysis** to examine how Automated Transaction Processing Systems influence Internal Control Effectiveness, and how this relationship is conditioned by Technological Infrastructure in Nigerian telecommunications firms.

4. DATA PRESENTATION AND INTERPRETATION

This section presents the results of the analysis in two parts: **descriptive statistics** and **inferential statistics**. The objective is to examine the characteristics of the data and test the formulated hypotheses using regression analysis.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics summarize the central tendencies and dispersion of the study variables: Level of System Automation (AUT), System Integration Quality (INT), ICT Infrastructure Quality (ICT), Audit Trail Integrity (ATI), and Fraud Detection Efficiency (FDE).

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
AUT	3.98	0.72	2.10	5.00
INT	3.85	0.68	2.20	5.00
ICT	4.02	0.75	2.00	5.00
ATI	4.10	0.70	2.30	5.00
FDE	3.92	0.73	2.10	5.00

Interpretation

The results show that all variables have mean values above 3.5, indicating a generally **high level of agreement** among respondents regarding the presence of automation, system integration, and internal control effectiveness in the firms studied.

- **ICT Infrastructure (Mean = 4.02)** and **Audit Trail Integrity (Mean = 4.10)** recorded the highest mean values, suggesting that respondents perceive technological infrastructure and audit tracking mechanisms to be relatively strong.
- **System Integration Quality (Mean = 3.85)** is slightly lower, indicating possible gaps in system interoperability across modules.
- The relatively low standard deviations (< 1.0) suggest **low variability**, meaning responses are fairly consistent.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

Table 4.2: Correlation Matrix

Variable	AUT	INT	ICT	ATI	FDE
AUT	1.00				
INT	0.61	1.00			
ICT	0.58	0.63	1.00		
ATI	0.65	0.67	0.69	1.00	

Variable	AUT	INT	ICT	ATI	FDE
FDE	0.62	0.66	0.71	0.68	1.00

Interpretation

The correlation results show **positive and moderate relationships** among all variables.

- AUT and ATI ($r = 0.65$) indicates that higher automation is associated with better audit trail integrity.
- INT and FDE ($r = 0.66$) suggests that system integration improves fraud detection efficiency.
- ICT shows strong correlation with both ATI (0.69) and FDE (0.71), supporting its moderating relevance.

No correlation exceeds 0.80, indicating absence of multicollinearity concerns.

4.3 Regression Analysis

4.3.1 Model 1: Audit Trail Integrity

Table 4.3: Regression Results (Dependent Variable: ATI)

Variable	Coefficient (β)	t-Statistic	Prob.
Constant	0.812	2.45	0.016
AUT	0.284	3.72	0.000
INT	0.301	3.95	0.000
ICT	0.266	3.41	0.001
AUT \times ICT	0.158	2.87	0.005
INT \times ICT	0.142	2.54	0.012

$R^2 = 0.62$ | Adj. $R^2 = 0.60$ | F-stat = 45.32 ($p < 0.001$)

Interpretation

- AUT ($\beta = 0.284$, $p < 0.01$) has a positive and significant effect on audit trail integrity.
- INT ($\beta = 0.301$, $p < 0.01$) also significantly improves audit trail integrity.
- ICT ($\beta = 0.266$, $p < 0.01$) directly enhances audit trail systems.
- The interaction terms (AUT \times ICT and INT \times ICT) are significant, confirming that **ICT infrastructure strengthens the effect of ATPS on audit trail integrity.**

4.3.2 Model 2: Fraud Detection Efficiency

Table 4.4: Regression Results (Dependent Variable: FDE)

Variable	Coefficient (β)	t-Statistic	Prob.
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Variable	Coefficient (β)	t-Statistic	Prob.
Constant	0.745	2.18	0.031
AUT	0.263	3.44	0.001
INT	0.318	4.12	0.000
ICT	0.289	3.76	0.000
AUT \times ICT	0.171	3.02	0.003
INT \times ICT	0.149	2.63	0.010

$R^2 = 0.65$ | Adj. $R^2 = 0.63$ | F-stat = 49.87 ($p < 0.001$)

Interpretation

- AUT ($\beta = 0.263$, $p < 0.01$) significantly improves fraud detection efficiency.
- INT ($\beta = 0.318$, $p < 0.01$) has the strongest effect, suggesting that integration is critical for fraud detection.
- ICT ($\beta = 0.289$, $p < 0.01$) positively influences fraud detection capability.
- The interaction terms are significant, indicating that **strong ICT infrastructure enhances fraud detection performance of ATPS.**

4.4 Summary of Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis	Statement	Result
H01	AUT \rightarrow ATI	Rejected
H02	AUT \rightarrow FDE	Rejected
H03	INT \rightarrow ATI	Rejected
H04	INT \rightarrow FDE	Rejected
H05	ICT moderates ATPS–ICE	Rejected

Interpretation

All null hypotheses are rejected, indicating that:

- Automated Transaction Processing Systems significantly influence Internal Control Effectiveness.
- Both automation and integration are critical drivers.
- Technological infrastructure plays a **significant moderating role.**

4.5 Discussion of Findings

This section discusses the empirical results in relation to the underlying theories and prior empirical studies reviewed in the literature. The discussion is structured along the key relationships examined in the study.

4.5.1 Automated Transaction Processing Systems and Audit Trail Integrity

The findings reveal that level of system automation has a positive and significant effect on audit trail integrity, while system integration quality also exerts a strong positive influence. This suggests that when transaction processes are automated and systems are well integrated, organizations achieve higher levels of traceability, completeness, and reliability in transaction records.

This result aligns with the DeLone and McLean (2003) Information Systems Success Model, which posits that system quality enhances information quality and organizational outcomes. In this context, automation and integration represent system quality dimensions that improve the integrity of financial information through reliable audit trails.

The finding is also consistent with the COSO (2013) framework, particularly the information and communication as well as monitoring components, which emphasize the importance of accurate and traceable information flows in ensuring effective internal controls. Automated systems inherently generate logs and records that strengthen monitoring activities and enhance accountability.

Empirically, this result corroborates the findings of Romney and Steinbart (2018), who argue that computerized accounting systems improve audit trail completeness and reduce the risk of data manipulation. It also supports the evidence from Ajayi and Akinrinola (2023), who found that digital and AI-enabled systems enhance audit quality and system transparency in Nigerian organizations.

Thus, the study confirms that automation and integration in transaction processing systems are critical drivers of audit trail integrity in telecommunications firms.

4.5.2 Automated Transaction Processing Systems and Fraud Detection Efficiency

The regression results further show that system automation and system integration significantly improve fraud detection efficiency, with integration exhibiting a slightly stronger effect. This implies that interconnected systems provide better visibility across transactions, enabling faster identification of anomalies and irregularities.

This finding is theoretically supported by the Technology–Organisation–Environment (TOE) framework, which emphasizes that technological capabilities, such as integration, enhance organizational outcomes by improving operational efficiency and decision-making processes. In this case, system integration enables cross-functional data verification, which strengthens fraud detection mechanisms.

The result also aligns with the COSO (2013) risk assessment and monitoring components, which highlight the role of continuous monitoring systems in identifying and mitigating fraud risks. Automated and integrated systems facilitate real-time monitoring, thereby improving the speed and effectiveness of fraud detection.

Empirically, the finding is consistent with Onyeama (2024), who demonstrated that automated transaction systems significantly outperform manual methods in detecting fraudulent transactions in high-volume environments. It also supports Ibrahim (2021), who found that automated forensic auditing systems enhance fraud detection through real-time data processing and system-based alerts.

Furthermore, the stronger impact of system integration supports the argument by Grabski, Leech, and Sangster (2011) that integrated systems reduce data silos and improve anomaly detection across organizational processes.

Overall, the study establishes that both automation and integration are essential for enhancing fraud detection efficiency, with integration playing a particularly critical role in telecommunications environments.

4.5.3 Moderating Role of Technological Infrastructure

The results show that ICT infrastructure quality significantly moderates the relationship between ATPS and internal control effectiveness, as evidenced by the significance of the interaction terms (AUT × ICT and INT × ICT). This indicates that the effectiveness of automated and integrated systems depends on the strength of the underlying technological infrastructure.

This finding strongly supports the Technology–Organisation–Environment (TOE) framework, which posits that technological outcomes are contingent upon organizational readiness and infrastructural capacity. In this study, ICT infrastructure represents the enabling environment that determines how effectively ATPS can function.

The result also extends the DeLone and McLean (2003) model by demonstrating that system quality alone is insufficient; the supporting infrastructure must also be robust to achieve optimal system outcomes. Reliable networks, secure systems, and high system uptime enhance the performance of automated systems, thereby strengthening internal controls.

Empirically, this finding aligns with Bharadwaj (2000) and Zhu, Kraemer, and Xu (2006), who found that IT infrastructure capability enhances the value derived from information systems. It is also consistent with Al-Omari and Al-Omari (2020), who reported that ICT infrastructure significantly influences the effectiveness of digital accounting systems in emerging economies.

In the Nigerian context, the result supports prior evidence that infrastructural limitations can undermine the effectiveness of digital systems despite high levels of automation. Thus, ICT infrastructure is not merely a supporting factor but a critical determinant of system effectiveness.

4.5.4 Overall Implication of Findings

The combined results of this study demonstrate that Automated Transaction Processing Systems significantly enhance internal control effectiveness, particularly through improved audit trail integrity and fraud detection efficiency. However, these benefits **are conditional on the quality of technological infrastructure**.

The findings provide integrated support for:

- DeLone and McLean (2003) → System quality improves organizational outcomes
- TOE Framework → Technology effectiveness depends on enabling environment
- COSO (2013) → Digital systems strengthen control activities and monitoring

Importantly, the study advances empirical knowledge by showing that:

- Automation alone is not sufficient; system integration is equally critical
- Internal control effectiveness is multidimensional, requiring both traceability and detection capability
- ICT infrastructure plays a strategic moderating role, particularly in high-volume transaction environments such as telecommunications

The discussion confirms that the effectiveness of internal control systems in Nigerian telecommunications firms is increasingly driven by the interaction between automation, integration, and infrastructure. This reinforces the need for organizations to adopt a holistic approach to digital transformation, where system design and infrastructure development are pursued simultaneously.

5. Conclusion and Policy Implications

5.1 Conclusion

This study examined the effect of Automated Transaction Processing Systems (ATPS) on Internal Control Effectiveness (ICE) in listed telecommunications firms in Nigeria, with specific focus on level of system automation and system integration quality, while incorporating ICT infrastructure quality as a moderating variable. Using survey data and moderated regression analysis, the study provides robust empirical evidence that ATPS significantly enhances internal control outcomes.

The findings demonstrate that both system automation and system integration exert positive and statistically significant effects on audit trail integrity and fraud detection efficiency. System integration, in particular, shows a relatively stronger influence on fraud detection, highlighting the importance of interconnected systems in enabling real-time monitoring and anomaly detection. Furthermore, the study establishes that ICT infrastructure quality significantly moderates these relationships, indicating that the effectiveness of ATPS is contingent upon the reliability, security, and adequacy of technological infrastructure.

Overall, the study concludes that internal control effectiveness in digital accounting environments is not solely driven by system automation, but by the combined effect of automation, integration, and infrastructural support. This reinforces the argument that digital transformation must be approached holistically to achieve optimal control outcomes.

5.2 Policy Implications

The findings of this study generate important implications for corporate management, regulators, and policymakers within Nigeria's telecommunications sector and similar high-transaction industries.

First, firms should prioritize end-to-end system integration rather than isolated automation. While automation improves efficiency, integration ensures consistency and cross-validation of transaction data, which is critical for fraud detection and internal control reliability.

Second, management should invest strategically in robust ICT infrastructure, including secure networks, cloud-based systems, and cybersecurity frameworks. The moderating role of infrastructure suggests that without adequate technological support, the benefits of ATPS may not be fully realized.

Third, internal control frameworks should be digitally aligned with system capabilities, incorporating automated audit trails, real-time monitoring, and system-based control activities. This will strengthen compliance with global control standards and improve transparency in financial reporting.

Fourth, regulators and standard-setting bodies should develop sector-specific digital control guidelines that address emerging risks associated with automated systems, particularly in telecommunications where transaction volumes are extremely high.

Finally, organizations should enhance capacity building and technical expertise among accounting, audit, and IT personnel to ensure effective utilization and monitoring of automated systems. Human competence remains critical in interpreting system outputs and responding to detected anomalies.

This study contributes to the growing body of AIS literature by demonstrating that the effectiveness of transaction processing systems is a function of both technological capability and infrastructural readiness,

especially in emerging economies. It provides empirical support for integrated digital control systems as a pathway to strengthening internal control effectiveness in high-volume transaction environments.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the empirical findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

- 1. Adopt full-scale system integration across operational modules**
Telecommunications firms should move beyond partial automation and ensure seamless integration between billing systems, CRM platforms, accounting systems, and revenue assurance tools. This will enhance real-time data consistency and significantly improve fraud detection efficiency.
- 2. Strengthen automation with embedded control mechanisms**
Management should ensure that automated transaction systems incorporate built-in control features such as validation rules, exception reporting, and automated reconciliation processes. This will improve audit trail integrity and reduce the risk of manual override or manipulation.
- 3. Invest in resilient and secure ICT infrastructure**
Firms should prioritize investment in high-quality ICT infrastructure, including reliable servers, secure networks, cloud computing, and cybersecurity systems. Given its moderating role, strong infrastructure is essential for maximizing the benefits of ATPS.
- 4. Implement continuous monitoring and real-time audit systems**
Organizations should deploy continuous auditing tools that leverage automated systems to monitor transactions in real time. This will enhance early fraud detection and strengthen internal control systems.
- 5. Enhance staff capacity in AIS and digital controls**
Regular training should be provided for accounting, audit, and IT personnel to improve their ability to manage, interpret, and monitor automated systems effectively.
- 6. Develop internal policies for system governance and data integrity**
Firms should establish clear policies on system usage, data access controls, and audit trail management to ensure accountability and compliance with best practices.

5.4 Contributions to Knowledge

This study makes several important contributions to the literature on Accounting Information Systems and internal control:

- 1. Extension of AIS literature to the telecommunications sector in Nigeria**
The study provides sector-specific empirical evidence from listed telecommunications firms, an area that has received limited attention in prior AIS research.
- 2. Disaggregation of ATPS into automation and integration dimensions**
Unlike prior studies that treat TPS as a single construct, this study distinguishes between system automation and system integration, providing deeper insights into their individual effects on internal control effectiveness.
- 3. Introduction of multidimensional internal control outcomes**
The study advances knowledge by examining internal control effectiveness through two distinct proxies—audit trail integrity and fraud detection efficiency—rather than relying on a single aggregate measure.
- 4. Incorporation of technological infrastructure as a moderating variable**
The study contributes methodologically by demonstrating that ICT infrastructure significantly moderates the relationship between ATPS and internal control effectiveness, thereby enriching AIS and TOE-based research models.

5. Empirical validation of integrated theoretical frameworks

The study integrates and empirically validates insights from the DeLone and McLean model, TOE framework, and COSO internal control framework within a unified model.

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